

PSYCHOLOGICAL STRATEGIES FOR SOCIAL AND EDUCATIONAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Communication is the foundation of all social and educational processes, and its psychological dimension plays a crucial role in shaping interpersonal relationships as well as in personal and professional development. This paper explores the **psychological strategies involved in social and educational communication**, highlighting how empathy, active listening, emotional self-regulation, and positive persuasion can influence the quality of interactions among teachers, students, parents, and the wider community. The theoretical framework is grounded in concepts from emotional intelligence (Goleman, 1995),

interpersonal communication psychology (Berne, 1964; Rogers, 1983), and relational pedagogy (Noddings, 2005). The empirical component, conducted on a sample of 80 teachers and school counselors, employs questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to analyze communicative competences and the psychological strategies used across diverse educational contexts. Findings emphasize the importance of a positive emotional climate, constructive feedback, and the ability to adapt messages to the needs and characteristics of the interlocutor. Moreover, a strong correlation emerges between teachers' emotional competences and students' level of engagement and motivation. The study concludes by underlining the need for continuous professional development in psychological communication and the integration of these strategies in classroom management and teacher education programs, in order to promote an educational environment based on trust, cooperation, and mutual respect.

Keywords: educational communication; emotional intelligence; empathy; self-regulation; teacher-student relationship.

Introduction

Both social and educational communication have a well-defined purpose, namely to put into practice the integral-vocational development of the human personality and for this reason, from a psychological point of view, they are subject to the general laws of assessment of any human activity in order to achieve the most effective results, using the most appropriate means suited to the anticipated goals and objectives.

Educational strategy, for example, refers to the approach of any human activity to achieve the best possible results with the most appropriate and suitable means for the purposes and objectives anticipated by the teacher in order to apply the "principles of learning in a practical training situation."

From this point of view, educational strategy becomes an essential part of psychological strategies for social and educational communication, recognized as, in fact, a teaching technology, as it is designated in the specialized literature. It follows that teaching technology is not limited to the use of technical means for transmitting information, but includes all components of the educational process in a unified whole, removing certain artificial boundaries between them and emphasizing the interdependence between content and all other aspects, such as organization, teacher-student relationships, methods, procedures used, etc. Therefore, the specialized literature reveals that teaching strategies occupy an important place within this teaching technology.

Discussions

Psychological analysis of these teaching strategies reveals that any teaching strategy involves two parameters:

- External programming, which refers to how teaching information is processed, organized, and presented. It is used to externally regulate the learning process and give it an organised character, guiding and directing this process while ensuring the independence and initiative of the learner.

- Internal operational programming, which refers to the register of mental components involved in the process of learning information. It facilitates internal self-regulation by capitalizing on the accumulated experience and psychological potential of each student.

In order to understand the psychological relevance of the educational strategy, we must grasp the specific nature of the relationships between these parameters, since between the two parameters, one referring to teaching activity and the other on learning, there is no unambiguous relationship due to the impossibility of fully connecting the two qualitatively distinct programs and the random factors that intervene.

1. First, a teaching strategy aims to establish and stabilize optimal relationships between teaching and learning activities, with a view to triggering psychological mechanisms appropriate to the age and individual characteristics of students and the specific conditions in which the learning process takes place. Any teaching strategy is effective only to the extent that, by transmitting a quantity of information, it succeeds in engaging students in its active and creative assimilation. Thus, the teaching process, as a process of knowledge, is determined by the logical structure of the content, as well as by the psychological characteristics of learning and communication. The mission of the teaching strategy is to ensure that the content is adapted to these particularities and, at the same time, to determine their internal movement on an upward trajectory.

2. Secondly, any teaching strategy operates within a field of factors and possibilities, and therefore its outcome includes a certain degree of probability. Any teaching strategy is thus stochastic or probabilistic in nature. The weight and role of random factors differ from one strategy to another.

3. Thirdly, any strategy requires a combination of teacher and student activity. From this point of view, the role of the teacher can shift from being merely a source of information to leading and controlling the independent activity of students, while their activity can shift from simple reproduction to creative activity. In this context, an important role is played by communication strategy, both social and educational.

The way in which social and educational communication strategies are implemented in practice can be considered an effective aid to educational outcomes. This "aid" is expressed by suggesting and creating situations that offer multiple possibilities, with the choice of solution being the result of a mental analysis process.

It is considered that some forms of these strategies focus on the teacher's activity (expository strategies), while others focus on the students' activity (heuristic strategies). Viewed abstractly, the differentiation seems arbitrary to us, because even if it is the students' activity aimed at discovering and assimilating knowledge, it is directed and coordinated by the teacher, operations that require at least as much effort as when the teacher exposes the knowledge. However, it is one thing to direct intellectual activity through heuristic methods, by analyzing alternatives and hypotheses, through successive searches, and another to do so through standardized, ready-made methods. The expository meaning of these strategies emphasizes the fact that some information is related by the teacher, while the heuristic meaning expresses the need to help and guide students in learning scientific truths.

Both approaches are necessary and indispensable, because not everything can be assimilated through independent research, and often there is no need for such research, as some of the objectives of the educational process, especially those of a formative nature, cannot be achieved by simply memorizing ready-made knowledge. It is important to decide where and when to use one approach or the other.

Lecturing is one of the main tools of verbal communication. With its help, the teacher has the opportunity to address a complex topic that synthesises a vast cognitive experience and a "model" of thinking, validated throughout the development of humanity, aspects that cannot be subjected to individual verification or discovered spontaneously by students.

B. We should say a few words about the psychological importance of social communication or public communication, as it is sometimes called.

In his work, Bernard Dagenais (2003) argues that the science of life is based on the principle of communication, and in this sense, things that are not

known, that are not communicated, do not exist. So communication is not a choice, it is necessary in order to exist, to make ourselves known, to develop. For this reason, in order to reach all members of its audience at the same time, to inform them and to be able to control and shape their opinion and image of it, it is necessary to resort to social communication or public communication, as it is also called (Narița, 2010).

Therefore, social communication must reach the public sphere, which is accessible to any individual, whether or not they are interested in the information found there. Public communication has the role of facilitating the pursuit of the public interest, which results from difficult arbitrations between individual and general interests, and because it is a bearer of general interest, communication in the public sphere is frequently threatened by the fact that it can be manipulated by any social actor or the media (David, 2008).

Communication is used not only in education but also to sell, to solve a particular problem, and to maintain public image. No product that is not known and promoted is accepted, just as no problem can be solved without a certain organization resorting to various communication techniques. Once a public image has been built, it must be maintained and strengthened because, over time, it fades, and this can only be avoided through communication.

Ideally, there should be no significant difference between the image projected within the organization and the image perceived externally by the public. To avoid this, the public relations specialist must ensure one of the basic principles of public communication, namely transparency. Transparency is a rule that must be respected by any organization, regardless of its field of activity, as it is particularly important for gaining public trust. Last but not least, the principle of transparency is important so that the organization's image corresponds to reality, is coherent, and tangible.

With regard to the organization's relationship with the outside world, the specialist must carry out communication activities in two main areas: communication with the local community and communication with the media. Communication with the local community is carried out through activities whose main purpose is to gain the sympathy, trust, and support of the public, while communication with the media encompasses all activities carried out to inform public opinion, without the certainty that the information it conveys will reach the public unaltered, as it first passes through the media filter.

There are quite a few situations in which public information is confused with advertising, the difference between them being that public information is the activity of presenting information to the public free of charge, while advertising is the purchase of time and space in one of the forms of mass media, through which a message is presented, the content, time, and place of which can be controlled by the buyer (Marconi, 2007).

When public information is used, the main purpose of social communication activities is to raise public awareness, but behind this purpose there are often other hidden intentions, such as influencing public opinion, promoting products or services, etc. In this regard, Joe Marconi points out that public information is not the game itself, but only the name of the game. When they want to communicate certain information about the organization, public relations professionals have the power to control the information they are about to convey, and because of this, they often highlight information that is advantageous and cover up information that could affect the organization in some way, and no one can accuse them of doing so because they are employed by the organization and are pursuing a common goal.

Regardless of the situation and the intentions of specialists in this field when considering the transmission of information, one thing is certain: in all

cases, the public message refers to legality and provides information about the appropriateness of an action, the procedure to be followed, the information to be provided, and the documents to be prepared; sometimes it reminds of the collective interest achieved in this way or of the shortcomings and sanctions in case the collective interest is forgotten.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the effectiveness of communication activities largely depends on the way the public perceives, interprets, and responds to the messages transmitted by an organization. Communication should not be regarded merely as the delivery of information, but as a complex and dynamic process that influences the relationship between institutions and society. Because public opinion is shaped by both rational and emotional factors, organizations must carefully consider the impact that their messages may have before making them public.

Any information disseminated by an organization should be consistent with the image, values, and objectives that it seeks to promote. In today's digital and highly interconnected environment, information spreads rapidly and becomes accessible to a wide audience almost instantly. Once released into the public sphere, messages can no longer be completely controlled or withdrawn, which increases the responsibility of organizations to ensure clarity, accuracy, and coherence in their communication strategies. A poorly constructed or misunderstood message may negatively affect credibility, trust, and institutional reputation.

Moreover, this analysis emphasizes the essential role of psychological perspectives in understanding social and educational communication. Public reactions are influenced not only by facts and logic, but also by emotions, beliefs, attitudes, and social experiences. For this reason, communication strategies must

take into account the psychological characteristics and expectations of the target audience in order to achieve meaningful and effective interaction.

In addition, social and educational communication plays an important role in shaping attitudes, encouraging social responsibility, and promoting constructive dialogue within society. Effective communication strategies can strengthen the relationship between institutions and the public, increase awareness of important issues, and contribute to the development of informed and engaged communities.

Therefore, we believe that incorporating psychological approaches into social and educational communication strategies is essential for ensuring effective public communication. Such an approach enables organizations to better understand audience behavior, anticipate public reactions, and create messages that are both credible and impactful in the context of contemporary society.

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